

The Crystalline Constituents of Euphorbiaceae: Part VII. The Triterpenes of *Euphorbia antiquorum*, Linn

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From the stems of *E. antiquorum* Linn, Friedelan 3 α -ol and its β -isomer, taraxerol and taraxerone have been isolated and identified. Taraxerol has also been noticed in the roots.

E. antiquorum, Linn.^{1,2} (Sans: Vajrakantaka) is an indigenous drug reputed as a stomachic and as a purgative³. This communication records the results of our examination of stems, and roots of this plant. The petroleum concentrate of the stems yielded a complex triterpene mixture from which friedelan 3 α - and 3 β -ols (fraction A), taraxerol (fraction B) and taraxerone ((fraction C) could be separated by fractional crystallisation. Chromatographic separation on alumina could be effected but proved to be laborious.

Fraction A, m.p. 277-79°, [α]_D³⁰ -1.12°, showed two spots in T.L.C. (chloroform, 0.2, 0.35) and the components could be effectively separated by benzoylating the mixture and then fractionating it from chloroform-methanol (1:1). Friedelan 3 α -ol benzoate was the first to separate, which was hydrolysed to yield friedelan 3 α -ol (I). The residual benzoate fraction gave on hydrolysis, friedelan 3 β -ol (II). Their identification was made by comparison with authentic samples and also by oxidation to friedelin⁴ (III).

(I) R = OH(α)

(II) R = OH(β)

(III) R = O

(IV) R = OH(β)

(V) R = O

Taraxerol (IV) is the major fraction of the light petroleum extract. Its reactions, I.R. and its derivatives agree closely with those recorded in literature⁵. Fraction C is a

1. Anjaneyulu, Nageswara Rao and Ramachandra Row., *Curr. Sci.*, 1964, 33, 583.
2. Sengupta and Ghosh, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 298.
3. Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants," Vol. 3, 2204.
4. Drake and Jacobsen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 1570.
5. Burrows and Simpson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2042.

a ketone, identical with taraxerone (V). Taraxerol (IV) has been also isolated from the roots of *E. antiquorum* in minute quantities. The action of NaBH_4 on taraxerone has been studied now. The reduced product was chromatographed over alumina and eluted with petroleum-benzene (1:1) and benzene. The former eluate gave taraxerol (IV) and the latter yielded a small quantity of an isomeric alcohol, m.p. 264-67°. It agrees with Takeda's isotaraxerol⁶ which was obtained by reduction with Na and amyl alcohol. Reduction with Na and ethanol or LiAlH_4 was reported to yield only taraxerol⁷ (IV).

The occurrence of friedelin together with the corresponding 3 α or/and 3 β alcohols is often reported in literature⁸. In *E. antiquorum*, Linn. friedelin has not been noticed.

EXPERIMENTAL

A. Stems of *E. antiquorum*, Linn

The dry stem-powder (300 g) was continuously extracted with light petroleum ether, and ethanol successively in a soxhlet apparatus.

The light yellow petroleum extract (2 l) was concentrated in three stages: (a) to 1.5 l. Fraction A (800 mg. crystallised from benzene as colorless prisms, m.p. 277-79°); (b) to 1 l. Fraction B (1.5 g., colorless needles from benzene, m.p. 274-76°, m.m.p. with A, 240-46°) and (c) to 500 ml. Fraction C (300 mg; colorless needles from chloroform-methanol, m.p. 237-38°).

The filtrate from fraction C, deposited only plant waxes on concentration.

Examination of Fraction B: Taraxerol.—Fraction B (500 mg.) was dissolved in benzene (20 ml) and passed over alumina (15g). Benzene eluate gave a solid (450 mg.) which crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (once) and benzene (twice) as colorless needles, m.p. 276-77°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2^\circ$ (C, 1.2 in CHCl_3). (Found: C, 84.35; H, 11.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.50; H, 11.74%). It gave a violet colour in the Burchard-Liebermann reaction and a yellow colour with tetranitromethane. λ_{max} 3580 cm^{-1} (OH), 1385 cm^{-1} and 1365 cm^{-1} (doublet, gem-dimethyl) and 815 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted C=C). Crude taraxerol was better purified through its benzoate.

Taraxeryl Acetate.—(Pyridine- Ac_2O) colorless prisms from benzene, m.p. 294-96°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 10^\circ$ (C, 1.2). (Found: C, 82.2; H, 11.4. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 82.06; H, 11.11%).

Taraxeryl Benzoate.—(Pyridine-benzoyl chloride at 100° for 1½ hr) crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (2 times) as colorless prisms, m.p. 282-84°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 30^\circ$ (C, 0.99). (Found: C, 83.52; H, 10.35. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 83.77; H, 10.21%).

Dihydrotaraxeryl Benzoate.—Taraxeryl benzoate (250 mg.) in glacial acetic acid-cyclohexane (30 ml; 1:1) was shaken with hydrogen in presence of Adam's catalyst. The theoretic

6. Takeda, *J. Pharm. Soc.*, Japan, 1941, 61, 117.

7. Koller, Hiestand, Dietrich and Jeger, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 33, 1051.

8. Jeffries, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 479; Courtney and Gascoigne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2115; Tanimoto and Noddaka Yahagi, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1958, 78, 304; Rangaswami and Sambamurthy, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1961, 54 A, 99; Shopper, Howden and Johnston, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 498; Arthur, Hui, Lam and (Miss) Saeio, *Ann. J. Chem.*, 1964, 17, 697; Chakravarti, Chakravarti and Samanta, *this Journal* 1964, 41, 859.

tical quantity of hydrogen (12 ml at 32°) was absorbed in 25 min. The dihydrotaraxeryl benzoate crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (2 times) as colorless prisms, m.p. 294-96°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 8^\circ$ (C, 1.1). (Found: C, 83.25; H, 10.3. $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 83.47; H, 10.53%).

Dihydrotaraxerol.—Dihydrotaraxeryl benzoate (100 mg.) in benzene (15 ml) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 8% ethanolic KOH (10 ml) for 5 hr. on a water bath. The dihydrotaraxerol crystallised from benzene (3 times) as short colorless needles, m.p. 266-67°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 20^\circ$ (C, 1.2). (Found: C, 84.21; H, 12.40. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.12; H, 12.15%).

Examination of Fraction C: Taraxerone.—Fraction C (300 mg.) was dissolved in benzene (20 ml) and passed over alumina. The benzene eluate (275 mg.) crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH (2 times) as colorless needles, m.p. 237-38°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 10^\circ$ (C, 0.98). (Found: C, 84.55; H, 11.40. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.89; H, 11.32%).

It gave a violet colour in the Burchard-Liebermann reaction and an intense purple colour in the Zimmermann test. It gave a yellow colour with tetranitromethane, λ_{max} 1705 cm^{-1} (C=O), 814 cm^{-1} (C=C).

Taraxerone Oxime.—(Pyridine-NH₂OH), colorless plates from CHCl_3 -MeOH, m.p. 291-93° (decomp.).

NaBH₄-reduction of Taraxerone.—Taraxerone (100 mg.) was taken in dioxan-methanol mixture (15 ml; 1:1), treated with excess NaBH₄ (20 mg.), and left overnight. The product was taken in benzene (5 ml) and chromatographed over alumina (15 g.). Light Petroleum benzene (80 ml; 1:1) eluted a colorless solid (75 mg.), m.p. 274-77° (Fraction I) and benzene (35 ml) eluted a colorless solid (15 mg), m.p. 264-67° (Fraction II).

Fraction I: Taraxerol.—It was crystallised from benzene (2 times) as colorless needles, m.p. 276-78°, unchanged by authentic taraxerol, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 2^\circ$ (C, 1.1). (Found: C, 84.25; H, 11.6. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.5; H, 11.74%).

Acetate (acetic anhydride and pyridine), m.p. 295-97°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 9^\circ$ (C, 0.98), unchanged by authentic taraxeryl acetate. *Benzoate* (benzoyl chloride and pyridine), m.p. 282-85°, unchanged by taraxeryl benzoate, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 32^\circ$ (C, 1.2).

Fraction II: Isotaraxerol.—It was crystallised from benzene as colorless needles, m.p. 266-68°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 13^\circ$ (C, 0.99). (Found: C, 84.30; H, 11.7. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.5; H, 11.74%).

Examination of Fraction A: Separation of Friedelan 3 α -ol and 3 β -ol.—Fraction A (800 mg.) was heated with pyridine (13 ml) and benzoyl chloride (6 ml) on a steam bath for 3½ hr. The colorless benzoate was fractionally crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH: compound A (400 mg.), colorless needles, m.p. 247-48°, compound B (200 mg), colorless prisms, m.p. 214-15° later raised to 252-54° by several crystallisations from CHCl_3 -MeOH.

Hydrolysis of Compound A: Friedelan 3 α -ol.—Compound A (100 mg.) in benzene (15 ml) was hydrolysed by refluxing with 8% ethanolic KOH (10 ml) for 3 hr. The product was crystallised from benzene (2 times) as colorless short needles, m.p. 300-301°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 20^\circ$. (Found: C, 84.20; H, 12.43. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$ requires C, 84.12; H, 12.15%).

Acetate, colorless plates, m.p. 310-12°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -14^\circ$. (Found: C, 81.4; H, 11.77. $C_{32}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 81.7; H, 11.49%.)

Hydrolysis of Compound B: Friedelan 3 β -ol.—Compound B (200 mg) was hydrolysed as before. The solid (175 mg.) was crystallised from benzene (2 times) as colorless plates, m.p. 288-89°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +14^\circ$ (C, 1.00). (Found: C, 84.3; H, 11.9. $C_{30}H_{32}O$ requires C, 84.12; H, 12.16%.)

Acetate, colorless plates, m.p. 293-95°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} +26^\circ$ (C, 1). (Found: C, 81.41; H, 11.8. $C_{32}H_{34}O_2$ requires C, 81.7; H, 11.49%.)

Chromic Acid Oxidation of Friedelan 3 α - and 3 β -ols: Friedelin.—Friedelan 3 α -ol (250 mg.) in benzene (25 ml) was treated with chromium trioxide (150 mg.) in 90% acetic acid (30 ml) and kept at the room temperature for 2½ hr. Excess CrO_3 was destroyed by means of methanol, water added, and extracted with ether. From the dried extract, a colorless solid (200 mg.) came out which was crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless needles, m.p. 260-62°, unchanged by authentic friedelin; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -25^\circ$ (C, 0.9). (Found: C, 84.27; H, 11.99. $C_{30}H_{30}O$ requires C, 84.15; H, 11.74%.)

Friedelan 3 β -ol was also similarly oxidised to friedelin.

(B) Roots of *E. antiquorum*, Linn.

The root-powder (1.5 kg.) was continuously extracted with ethanol for 32 hr. The deep brown extract (5 l.) was concentrated to 1 litre and the waxes were removed by filtration. The filtrate was now evaporated in vacuum and the residual brown viscous oil (70 g) was treated with light petroleum (3×300 ml) and benzene (3×300 ml) and the undissolved solid rejected.

The light petroleum fraction (900 ml) was concentrated to furnish colorless plates (50 mg.) m.p. 90°, negative to the Barchard-Liebermann test.

The benzene fraction (900 ml) was concentrated to 30 ml and chromatographed over alumina (100 g). The column was eluted with light petroleum, benzene, and ether. Light petroleum and ether fractions did not yield any crystalline solid. Benzene eluted a colorless solid (100 mg.), twice recrystallised when it came out as colorless needles, m.p. 279-80°, undepressed with authentic taraxerol. Acetate, m.p. 294-95°. Benzoate, m.p. 283-85°.

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